

CHEMICAL SCIENCES**ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ АДсорбЦИОННО – СТРУКТУРНЫХ СВОЙСТВ ПРИРОДНОГО И
ОБРАБОТАННЫХ МОНТМОРИЛЛОНИТА****Иманова Н.**

*Ведущий научный сотрудник,
Институт Катализа и Неорганической химии
Министерства Науки и Образования Азербайджанской Республики*

Зарбалиева И.

*Доктор химических наук,
Бакинская Высшая Школа Нефти, Азербайджан*

Мамедова С.

*старший научный сотрудник,
Институт Катализа и Неорганической химии
Министерства Науки и Образования Азербайджанской Республики*

Алиева Г.

*Ведущий научный сотрудник,
Институт Катализа и Неорганической химии
Министерства Науки и Образования Азербайджанской Республики*

Рахманова С.

*Научный сотрудник,
Институт Катализа и Неорганической химии
Министерства Науки и Образования Азербайджанской Республики*

Мамедова Н.

*Научный сотрудник,
Институт Катализа и Неорганической химии
Министерства Науки и Образования Азербайджанской Республики*

Рзаева А.

*Старший специалист,
Бакинская Высшая Школа Нефти, Азербайджан*

**STUDY OF ADSORPTION-STRUCTURAL PROPERTIES OF NATURAL AND PROCESSED MONT-
MORILLONITE****Imanova N.**

*Leading researcher,
Institute of Catalysis and Inorganic Chemistry, Ministry of Science and Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan*

Zarbaliyeva I.

*Doctor of Chemical Sciences,
Baku Higher Oil School, Azerbaijan*

Mammadova S.

*Senior researcher,
Institute of Catalysis and Inorganic Chemistry,
Ministry of Science and Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan*

Aliyeva Q.

*Leading researcher,
Institute of Catalysis and Inorganic Chemistry,
Ministry of Science and Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan*

Rahmanova S.

*Scientific worker,
Institute of Catalysis and Inorganic Chemistry,
Ministry of Science and Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan*

Mammadova N.

*Scientific worker,
Institute of Catalysis and Inorganic Chemistry,
Ministry of Science and Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan*

Rzayeva A.

*Senior specialist,
Baku Higher Oil School, Azerbaijan*

Аннотация

Создание научных основ приготовления и применения эффективных адсорбентов на основе природных монтмориллонита делает необходимым исследование природы активных центров, обменных катионов, а также свободной пористости структур их адсорбционного пространства и выяснение влияния этих факторов на адсорбционные процессы. Задачей отдельных исследований является создание адсорбентов на основе природных бентонитов для конкретных сорбционных процессов. Для приготовления на их основе эффективных адсорбентов и катализаторов необходимо исследовать пористоструктурные характеристики в зависимости от различных факторов и возможность регулирования их поверхностных свойств. Исследованы пористоструктурные свойства природного и Co^{2+} -форм монтмориллонита на основе изотерм адсорбции-десорбции воды и бензола. Показано, что химическое и структурное модифицирование позволяет изменять физико-химические свойства бентонитов и значительно расширить области возможного их применения.

Abstract

In order to study the adsorption-structural properties of natural and processed montmorillonite and to prepare effective adsorbents and catalysts based on them, it is necessary to study the porous structural characteristics depending on various factors and the possibility of regulating their surface properties. The porous structural properties of natural form Co^{2+} -form montmorillonite based on adsorption-desorption isotherms of water and benzene. The purpose of the work is to study the porous structural characteristics of montmorillonite on the adsorption of benzene and water vapor using the BET method. The structure and distribution of pore volume along the radius of natural montmorillonite was studied and it was revealed that in montmorillonite there are pores that differ from each other in diameter. Based on the isotherm of benzene, water taken from deposit in Agdere region of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

Ключевые слова: монтмориллонит, бензол, адсорбция.

Keywords: montmorillonite, benzol, adsorption.

In republic of Azerbaijan, there are large deposits of natural crystalline aluminosilicates of industrial importance. To prepare effective adsorbents and catalysts based on them, it is necessary to study the pore-structural characteristics depending on various factors.

When studying the geometric structure of sorbents obtained on the basis of natural aluminosilicates, it is necessary to have adsorption isotherms of vapors of various substances for a quantitative study and comparison of the intermolecular interactions of the adsorbent-adsorbate that occur during adsorption, as well as data on changes in the physicochemical properties of the surface of the sorbents depending on various factors [1].

The adsorption-desorption isotherms of adsorbate vapors have an S-shaped structure, due to the sequential filling of the pores of sorbents obtained on the basis of natural crystalline aluminosilicates [2].

The study of the chemistry and surface texture of sorbents is of particular interest in view of the fact that it is the surface that serves as the interface between the adsorbent and the liquid or gaseous phases.

It should be noted that all sorption processes of vapor gases begin with the act of adsorption on the external surface of sorbents and catalysts that are important [3]. At very low relative vapor pressures, especially in the case of strong adsorption on an adsorbent with a non-uniform surface, equilibrium is usually established very slowly.

EXPERIMENTAL PART

For the experimental study, montmorillonite from the Agdere deposit was used. The determination method is described in works [4].

The method for obtaining Co^{2+} -forms of montmorillonite is described in detail in the literature [5-6].

Adsorption-desorption isotherms of water and benzene vapors on sorbent samples were measured using a vacuum installation with a McBan-Bakr quartz balance. To measure the specific surface area using the BET method, it is sufficient to carry out adsorption to a relative pressure of 0.3-0.4 mmHg. In this case, the rate of establishment of adsorption equilibrium depends on the nature of the adsorbent.

The sorbents were pre-evacuated for 6 hours at a temperature of 20°C.

In figure 1 the adsorption isotherms of water vapor at a temperature of 20°C by natural montmorillonite are presented. As can be seen from figure 1, polar molecules with small diameters (like water) easily penetrate into the micropores of natural montmorillonite due to ion-dipole interaction with exchange cations located on the micropores of montmorillonite. This process corresponds to a circular rise in the water adsorption isotherm in the region of relatively low pressures at $P/P_s=0.30-0.40$. At this stage, water adsorption occurs due to the filling of the remaining unoccupied space of the micropores of the sorbent with the adsorbate. Up to $P/P_s = 0.9$, adsorbed water molecules form hydrogen bonds between themselves and exchange cations from the first coordination sphere of the sorbent, while the adsorption curve of the Co^{2+} -form of montmorillonite rises sharply to $P/P_s = 0.9$. This indicates the presence in the sorbent there are more developed secondary transition pores.

Figure 1. Isotherms of adsorption- desorption of water vapor for natural bentonites

From the water vapor adsorption isotherm, one can get an idea of the structural characteristics of the adsorbent [7].

Figure 2 shows the adsorption-desorption isotherms of water vapor on the Co^{2+} -form of montmorillonite.

As a result, a comparison of the adsorption-desorption isotherms of water vapor on natural and its Co^{2+} -form montmorillonite shows that after treating bentonite with cobalt salt, the shape of the isotherm changes, which indicates an increase in the adsorption capacity of the sample with respect to water molecules.

Figure 2. Isotherms of adsorption-desorption of water vapor with Co^{2+} form of bentonite

Figure 3 shows the kinetic curve of the adsorption of water vapor on natural montmorillonite and Co^{2+} -forms at $P = 18 \text{ mm Hg}$. It follows from the figure that within 60 minutes about 80% of the micropore volume is filled with water molecules, the sorbent is saturated water, and then the curve runs parallel to the x-axis. From a comparison of the kinetic curves of vapor adsorption on natural and Co^{2+} - form montmorillonite, it

can be seen that the adsorption capacity of water vapor on Co^{2+} -form is greater than on natural montmorillonite. Within 40 minutes it occurs filling the total volume of micropores with Co^{2+} -form of montmorillonite by 85-70%, respectively.

Figure 3. Kinetic curve of vapor adsorption on Co^{2+} - forms (2) and natural montmorillonites (1)

Figure 4 shows the adsorption-desorption isotherms of benzene at a temperature of 20°C on samples of montmorillonite taken from the Agdere region's deposits. As can be seen from the isotherms and critical

curves of adsorption-desorption at $P/P_s=0.8$, the isotherm rises higher, which shows that there is a developed mesopore in the porous structure of montmorillonite [8].

Figure 4. Isotherm of benzene adsorption on natural bentonite

From the adsorption-desorption isotherm of benzene vapor on the Co^{2+} form of montmorillonite presented in figure 5, it follows that when the partial pressure of benzene is increased to $P/P_s = 0.20-25$, the formation of a monolayer with a low-energy surface is completed. On the adsorption-desorption isotherms of benzene vapor Co^{2+} -montmorillonite exhibits a sharp increase in sorption at P/P_s close to 1. This can be explained by the fact that on the secondary porous structure of montmorillonite there are quite large pores in which benzene vapors condense.

Benzene molecules do not penetrate into the interpacket space of the Co^{2+} form of montmorillonite; their adsorption occurs on the outer surface of the sample and is adsorbed only in the secondary porous space of its crystals [9]. From the isotherms and critical curves of adsorption-desorption at $P/P_s=0.8$, the isotherm rises higher, which shows that there are mesopores developed in the porous structure of montmorillonite.

Figure 5. Isotherm of benzene adsorption on Co^{2+} forms of bentonite

The comparison of the adsorption-desorption isotherms of benzene vapor on Co^{2+} -forms of montmorillonite and natural ones showed that they differ from each other in the shape and number of adsorbed benzene molecules. This study proves that the changes on chemical properties of montmorillonite will significantly expand the areas of its possible applications [10-11].

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